

Appendix_A1: Glossary of terms

Term	Definition	Category	Example/Application	Relevance to Study	Citation/References
<i>Spatial Knowledge</i>	Understanding of the relationships between objects in space, including their position, size, shape, and orientation.	Cognitive Skills	Understanding map layouts.	Fundamental for developing spatial reasoning in STEM education.	Poepper et al. (2020)
<i>Spatial Awareness</i>	Recognition of the spatial relationship between oneself and the environment or between objects in space.		Navigating through a maze.	Crucial for understanding spatial relationships in STEM fields.	Karnath et al. (2001) Ishikawa (2021)
<i>Spatial Learning</i>	The acquisition of knowledge and skills related to spatial concepts and reasoning.		Teaching map-based problem solving.	Core for understanding spatial concepts and their applications.	Chrastil and Warren (2012)
<i>Spatial Thinking Strategies</i>	Methods and approaches used to solve problems involving spatial relationships, such as breaking down complex shapes or imagining transformations.		Breaking down 3D objects into simpler parts.	Key for solving spatial problems in STEM contexts.	Metoyer et al. (2015) Newcombe (2017)
<i>Spatial Thinking</i>	The cognitive process of visualizing and reasoning about spatial relationships.		Solving puzzles that require spatial visualization.	Central to developing spatial reasoning skills in students.	Uttal and Cohen (2012)
<i>Spatial Competence</i>	The ability to understand and manipulate spatial relationships effectively.		Practicing real-world tasks like reading blueprints or maps.	Vital for solving practical problems involving spatial reasoning.	Newcombe and Learmonth (2005)
<i>Spatial Aptitude</i>	The innate or learned capacity for spatial reasoning and visualization.		Measuring natural aptitude for spatial problem-solving.	Relates to identifying and leveraging natural spatial talents.	Lord and Nicely (1997)
<i>Spatial Teaching</i>	Teaching methods and practices that focus on helping students develop an understanding of spatial relationships, visualization, and spatial reasoning skills.	Teaching Strategies	Using visual aids to teach geometry.	Key for equipping teachers with strategies to improve spatial reasoning in students.	Lord (1987)
<i>Teach Spatial Ability</i>	Educational strategies aimed at improving students' ability to perceive, manipulate, and reason about spatial relationships.		Teaching students how to visualize molecular structures.	Aims to directly enhance students' spatial reasoning skills.	Uttal et al. (2013)
<i>Teaching and Practice of Spatial Ability</i>	The combination of instructional strategies and practical exercises aimed at fostering spatial reasoning skills.		Combining spatial exercises with lectures.	Blends practice with theoretical teaching for spatial improvement.	Huang and Lin (2017)
<i>Spatial Pedagogies</i>	Teaching methods that focus on engaging students in spatial thinking and reasoning.		Engaging students with hands-on 3D modeling projects.	Highlights practical methods for teaching spatial concepts.	Lim et al. (2012)
<i>Spatial-Related Pedagogy</i>	Teaching practices that explicitly aim to improve spatial reasoning and skills.		Incorporating map-based tasks into STEM curricula.	Focuses teaching efforts on spatial thinking strategies.	Pollitt et al. (2020)

<i>Spatial Instruction</i>	The process of teaching and learning spatial concepts and skills.		Teaching geometry using spatial reasoning examples.	Supports a focused approach to teaching spatial reasoning.	Hsi et al. (1997)
<i>Levels of Spatial Ability</i>	The hierarchical stages or levels in developing spatial reasoning ability.	Developmental Processes	Identifying students' spatial reasoning stage and providing targeted support.	Helps tailor teaching to individual student abilities.	Carter et al. (1987) Fiantika and Setyawati (2019)
<i>Spatial Development</i>	The overall development of spatial reasoning through education and experience.		Providing opportunities for hands-on learning with spatial tasks.	Ensures continuous growth in spatial reasoning abilities.	Newcombe et al. (2013)
<i>Spatialized Curriculum</i>	Curriculum designed to integrate spatial reasoning and skills across subjects.	Curriculum Design	Using spatial reasoning in history lessons for map analysis.	Key to integrating spatial reasoning across STEM education.	Ashton et al. (2020) Lin et al. (2024)
<i>Spatial Classrooms</i>	Classroom designs or settings optimized for spatial learning, such as VR-equipped spaces.	Classroom Design	Using AR to visualize complex 3D structures in class.	Provides an optimal environment for teaching spatial skills.	Lim et al. (2012)
<i>Spatial Activities</i>	Tasks or exercises designed to engage and improve spatial thinking, such as puzzles, 3D modeling, or map reading.	Activities	Solving jigsaw puzzles.	Provides hands-on approaches to practice spatial thinking.	Mccormack (2017) Giraud (2017) Uttal et al. (2013)
<i>Spatial Training</i>	Activities and exercises explicitly designed to strengthen spatial reasoning and problem-solving.		Solving 3D construction puzzles.	Applies structured practices for spatial skill improvement.	Stieff and Uttal (2015)
<i>Spatial Experiences</i>	Real-world or simulated interactions that provide opportunities to practice and develop spatial reasoning.		Participating in VR-based simulations.	Connects theory with real-world applications.	Baenninger and Newcombe (1989) Voyer et al. (2000)
<i>Spatial Tasks</i>	Specific activities or problems that require spatial reasoning for their completion.		Solving 3D block puzzles or geometry problems.	Directly engages students in spatial reasoning activities.	Kordjamshidi et al. (2010)
<i>Spatial Technology</i>	Technological tools and platforms that support spatial reasoning, such as GIS or 3D modeling software.	Technology	Using GIS to teach geographic concepts.	Supports innovative teaching with advanced technological tools.	Ley et al (2009)

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